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Precipitation driven nano-twinning: Simultaneous enhancement of mechanical and electrical properties in Cu-Ni-Sn alloys

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ABSTRACT

After homogenization, hot forging and solid-solution treatment at 800 °C, the Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy was cold-rolled to a 60 % thickness reduction and aged at 400 °C. After 1 h aging, spinodal decomposition produced the Sn and Ni enriched DO₂₂ phase coherent with the matrix, while abundant nanotwins emerged in the vicinity of (Cu, Ni)₃Sn precipitates in the recrystallized matrix. Compared to the as-rolled state, the alloy exhibited enhanced hardness (316 HV), ultimate tensile strength (1131 MPa), and electrical conductivity (9.7 % IACS). Extending aging to 4 h led to extensive (Cu, Ni)₃Sn secondary phase formation and pronounced recrystallization, reducing strength to 855 MPa but increasing electrical conductivity to 11.7 % IACS and total elongation to 12.9 %. The synergistic interplay of spinodal decomposition, local recrystallization, precipitation and nano-twinning underpinned the superior mechanical and electrical properties of the 1 h aged Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy.

The Cu-Ni-Sn alloys, known for their exceptional mechanical properties, wear resistance, and corrosion resistance, are promising substitutes for beryllium-copper alloys [1,2]. They excel in high-load applications like aircraft landing gears and marine engineering [3,4]. The Cu-15Ni-8Sn alloy is a precipitation hardening system that undergoes spinodal decomposition and is typically strengthened through deformation and aging [5,6]. Extensive research has been conducted on the aging behavior of these alloys after cold pre-deformation [7,8], which demonstrates that the numerous dislocations and twins generated during deformation not only strengthen the alloy [9,10] but also accelerate the aging process [11,12]. Aging induces phase transformations, e.g., spinodal decomposition and discontinuous precipitation, forming ordered DO₂₂, L₁₂ and γ -(Cu, Ni)₃Sn phases [13,14].

It is widely acknowledged that the DO₂₂ and L₁₂ phases are generated within the matrix via spinodal decomposition [15]. These phases are minuscule in size and maintain a highly coherent relationship with the matrix, and greatly enhance the mechanical properties of the alloy. Nonetheless, as the aging time increases, discontinuous precipitation of the γ phase occurs at the grain boundaries of the alloy [16,17].

Abundant research demonstrates that the precipitation of the γ phase notably deteriorates the strength and also leads to a substantial reduction in fracture elongation [18,19]. Stabilizing thermodynamic properties of Cu-Ni-Sn alloys remains a challenge. Crystallographic defects such as dislocations, twin boundaries (TB), and hard precipitates are keys to strengthening [20,21], with dislocations and precipitates well-documented in the literature upon deformation-aging treatments [22,23]. However, nanotwins are only observed under certain severe plastic deformation conditions, with an extremely low volume fraction [24–26]. Zhou et al. [27] observed nanotwins near discontinuous precipitates in Mn-doped Cu-9Ni-6Sn aged at 350 °C, but the twinning mechanism remains unclear, which may be related to the decrease in the stacking fault energy (SFE) caused by the addition of Mn.

Adjusting the SFE via composition enables multiple strengthening mechanisms in face center cubic (FCC) alloys [28]. In Cu-Ni-Sn alloys, the SFE decreases with decreasing Ni content and increasing Sn content [29–31]. Here, we increased the Sn content by 1 wt. % compared to the popular Cu-15Ni-8Sn alloy, to explore its effect on the microstructure evolution and precipitation behavior during aging treatment after

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deformation, as well as the influence on the mechanical and electrical properties.

A Cu-15Ni-9Sn (wt. %) alloy was produced by air induction melting from high-purity metal blocks. The as-cast ingot was then subjected to a homogenizing treatment at 840 °C for 4 h to reduce segregation, followed by hot forging and a solid solution at 800 °C for 1 h. After air cooling, the samples underwent cold rolling with a reduction of 60 %. The specimens were then aged at 400 °C. The rolling plane was selected for hardness testing and most microstructural characterization. The specimens for optical microscopy analysis were etched in a solution of 3 g FeCl₃ + 100 mL ethanol. Hardness tests were conducted using an HV-30Z/LCD Vickers hardness tester with a load of 98 N applied for 10 s. An electronic universal testing machine (CMT5105, Sansi) was used for tensile tests for samples with a gauge size of 2 × 1.5 × 20 mm³, at a strain rate of 5 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹; each group was tested at least three times along the rolling direction (RD). The electrical resistivity was precisely measured via a HIOKI-RM3548 ohmmeter, achieving an error within 0.1 μΩ, and the electrical conductivity was estimated relative to the International Annealed Copper Standard (% IACS). The crystal structure was analyzed using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Bruker D8 Advance) with a scanning range from 40° to 100°. The microstructure was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Zeiss Gemini300) equipped with an electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) system, and a transmission electron microscope (TEM, Talos F200X or JEM-2100). The detailed sample preparation process is presented in Supplement 1.1. Needle-shaped specimens required for atom probe tomography (APT) were fabricated by lift-outs and annular milled in a FEI Scios focused ion beam/scanning electron microscope (FIB/SEM). The APT characterizations were performed in a local electrode atom probe (CAMEACA LEAP

5000 XR). The specimens were analyzed at 50 K in voltage mode, a pulse repetition rate of 200 kHz, a pulse fraction of 20 %, and an evaporation detection rate of 0.4 % atom per pulse. Imago Visualization and Analysis Software (IVAS) version 3.8 was used for 3D reconstructions and data analysis.

Fig. 1 presents the microstructure of the 60 % cold-rolled Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy. On the rolling plane, both the optical micrograph (Fig. 1a) and the EBSD map (Fig. 1b) show that the grains are elongated along the RD and the deformation bands are parallel to the transverse direction (TD). On the RD-ND (normal direction) plane (Fig. 1c), it can be seen that the grains are compressed along the ND and elongated along the RD, and the deformation bands are inclined about 40° to the RD. The TEM image (Fig. 1d) shows a high dislocation density, forming entanglements and substructures. The APT maps (Fig. 1e) of Cu, Ni and Sn exhibit no element segregation. Apart from that, a small number of nanotwins were found in the deformed microstructure (Fig.1f-i).

The 60 % cold-rolled Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy was aged at 400 °C. Hardness (Fig. 2a) starts at 289 HV, peaks at 316 HV after 1 h of aging, then decreases to approximately 240 HV with longer aging. Samples aged for 1 h and 4 h were selected for further study. XRD (Fig. 2b) shows that the cold-rolled and 1 h aged samples retain FCC structure, while 4 h aging induces minor γ precipitation, with peak shifts confirming precipitation from the FCC matrix. The tensile properties of the selected samples are shown in Fig. 2c. The results indicate that the ultimate tensile strength of the sample aged for 1 h is 1131 MPa, which is increased by approximately 17.1 % compared to the cold-rolled sample (966 MPa). After aging for 4 h, the sample retains a strength of 855 MPa with a higher elongation of 12.9 %. The electrical conductivity exhibits a monotonic increase with the extension of the aging time, rising from 6.6 % IACS

Fig. 1. Microstructure of the cold-rolled alloy: (a) optical micrograph, (b) IPF-RD coloring map of the rolling plane, (c) IPF-RD coloring map of the longitudinal plane, (d) bright-field TEM micrograph and corresponding selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern, (e) APT reconstructed atom maps of Cu, Ni and Sn, (f) high-magnification TEM image show the nanotwin bundles, (g) high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) image of the nanoscale deformation twins, (h) fast Fourier transform (FFT) pattern of g, (i) inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) image of the red square in g.

Fig. 2. Properties and comparison. (a) The variation of hardness over the aging time, (b) XRD results showing the phase evolution during aging, (c) tensile stress-strain curves, (d) tensile strength and electrical conductivity comparison of the presented Cu-Ni-Sn alloys with those reported in [1,32–37].

(cold-rolled) to 9.7 % IACS (1 h aged) and 11.7 % IACS (4 h aged). Compared to other Cu-Ni-Sn alloys (Figs. 2d and S2), the 1 h aged Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy exhibits a superior tensile strength with moderate fracture elongation and electrical conductivity, while the 4 h aged sample exhibits a good balance of tensile strength, fracture elongation, and electrical conductivity [1,32–37].

The microstructure of 1 h aged samples is presented in Fig. 3a. The EBSD analysis shows extensive recrystallized grains of a weaker texture (Fig. S1a, b) compared to the deformed structure (Fig. S1c, d). Fig. 3b shows that the recrystallized region has a low kernel average misorientation (KAM). Additionally, the γ phase was detected in the recrystallized region with a volume fraction of 2.9 %.

TEM analysis (Fig. 3c) shows discontinuous precipitates nucleating at grain boundaries and growing following the recrystallization boundary migration. The recrystallized region consists of the α phase rich in Cu and the γ phase rich in Ni and Sn (Fig. 3d). Upon magnifying the region M in Fig. 3c, it can be observed that significant spinodal decomposition occurred in the deformed structure (Fig. 3e). SAED (Fig. 3f) reveals one of the resultant phases, i.e. the DO_{22} phase (Fig. 3f), exhibiting orientation relationship $(1\bar{1}1)_{\text{Cu}} // (\bar{1}12)_{\text{DO}_{22}}$, $[110]_{\text{Cu}} // [110]_{\text{DO}_{22}}$.

Different from the lamellar structure of the α and γ phases formed by discontinuous precipitation during the conventional aging process of Cu-Ni-Sn alloys [6,38], a large number of nanotwins were found nearly parallel to the γ lamellae within recrystallized grains in the 1 h aged

Fig. 3. The microstructure after aging at 400 °C for 1 h. (a) IPF-RD coloring map, (b) KAM map, (c) TEM micrograph showing discontinuous precipitation, (d) dark-field TEM micrograph showing precipitates in the recrystallized structure and corresponding element distribution maps, (e) dark-field TEM image of the DO_{22} phase, (f) SAED patterns of e.

sample (Fig. 4a). The HRTEM and FFT images (Fig. 4b and c) show that the γ and α phases conform to the orientation relationship of $(111)\alpha // (001)\gamma$, $[011]\alpha // [010]\gamma$. Compared with the deformation twins formed during the rolling process, the annealing twins formed during aging exhibit significantly higher density and greater thickness (Fig. 4d). While annealing twins are generally coarser than deformation twins, their high density here is attributed to the high density of nanoscale precipitates. Precipitation generates a local strain field within the matrix, lowering the activation energy for twin nucleation and fostering nanotwin formation adjacent to γ lamellae in the recrystallized grains [39]. In addition to the lamellar γ phase, a large number of bulk γ precipitates are also formed in the α matrix (Fig. S3) and nanotwins are

adjacent to the phase boundaries (Fig. 4e-h). The formation of nanotwins serves as a critical mechanism for grain refinement, which leads to a substantial enhancement in the strength of the alloy. Simultaneously, the twin boundaries exhibit remarkable characteristics of perfect coherency and sharpness in relation to the matrix, and thus the electron scattering arising from twin boundaries is negligible [40,41]. As a consequence, the aged Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy is capable of preserving both elevated strength and excellent electrical conductivity. According to the APT results (Fig. 4i and j), the γ precipitates are mainly rich in Ni and Sn, with an average element concentration (at. %) of 16.6 % Cu, 58.1 % Ni and 25.3 % Sn. In the α phase, the elemental composition is 85.9 % Cu, 12 % Ni, and 2.03 % Sn, and the Ni content is much lower than that in

Fig. 4. Discontinuous precipitation and twinning after aging at 400 °C for 1 h. (a) Bright-field image and element distributions, in which the yellow arrows indicate the γ phase, (b) HRTEM of precipitates and twins, (c) FFT of the red square in b, (d) bright-field image of precipitates and nanotwins, (e) HRTEM of a precipitate and twins, (f) IFFT image of the phase boundary marked by the red square in e, (g) HRTEM of a precipitate, (h) IFFT image of the red rectangle in g, (i) APT results of the α and γ phases, (j) variation of element contents from α to γ phase.

the previously reported Cu-15Ni-8Sn alloys [21,42].

Fig. 5 presents the microstructure of Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy aged at 400 °C for 4 h. EBSD (Figs. 5a and S4g) reveals nearly complete recrystallization compared to the 1 h aged (Fig. S4d) and cold-rolled (Fig. S4a) samples, with almost random grain orientations and an average grain size of 1.64 μm (Fig. S1e and f). The γ phase volume fraction increases to 6.9 %, precipitating predominantly at grain boundaries (Fig. 5b). The fraction of twin boundaries rises from 3.2 % (cold-rolled) and 5.8 % (1 h aged) to 25.4 % (Fig. S4b, e, h). TEM analysis (Fig. 5c) shows submicron recrystallized grains and numerous lamellae precipitates. Magnifying area A (Fig. 5d) reveals a lamellar structure composed of the γ phase, α phase, and nanotwins, with an average width of the γ lamella about 46 nm, larger than that in the 1 h aged sample. The line scans (Fig. 5e) confirm γ phase rich in Ni and Sn and α phase rich in Cu. In area B (Fig. 5f), intragranular γ precipitates retard the boundary migration of the recrystallizing grains. Through a statistical assessment of the KAM (Figs. S4c, f, i), it has been determined that the stored energy decreased significantly as the aging time is extended, but there are still a few non-recrystallized regions with relatively high stored energy. In addition, spherical particles and γ lamellae precipitated at the grain boundaries maintain a coherent relationship with the matrix (Fig. 5 g-i).

Mechanical properties are linked to the microstructure. Here, the strength and ductility of the Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy change as the microstructure evolves during aging. The yield strength (σ_y) arises from multiple mechanisms [43],

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_0 + \sigma_{dis} + \sigma_{gb} + \sigma_{ss} + \sigma_{ps} \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 is lattice friction stress, σ_{dis} is dislocation strengthening, σ_{gb} is grain boundary (including twinning boundary) strengthening, σ_{ss} is solution strengthening, and σ_{ps} is precipitation strengthening (details in Supplement 1.3). Calculations for cold-rolled and 4 h aged samples align well with experimental values, though quantifying DO₂₂ phase strengthening from spinodal decomposition in the 1 h aged sample proves challenging. The result indicates that for the cold-rolled sample, the mechanical strength comes primarily from dislocation, grain boundary and solid solution strengthening. In contrast, for the 1 h aged sample, dislocation and solid solution contributions decrease, while spinodal decomposition, precipitation, and nanotwin induced grain refinement dominate. For the sample aged for 4 h, the lamellar structures of γ, α, and the nanotwins jointly contribute to the relatively high tensile strength (Fig. S5). The tensile elongation in Cu-Ni-Sn alloys typically decreases with increasing size of γ precipitates and volume fraction [18,19]. However, the elongation of the 4 h aged sample was significantly improved. This is because (i) the coherent interfaces between α, γ and nanotwins permit dislocation transfer and thus reduce stress concentration, (ii) a low dislocation density in the α phase allows dislocation accumulation and hardening, and (iii) the α phase acts as a soft matrix that relaxes stress concentration at interfaces. The corresponding tensile fracture (Fig. S6) and the work hardening analysis of the 4 h sample (Fig. S7) are presented in Supplement 1.4.

Fig. 5. Microstructure after aging at 400 °C for 4 h. (a) IPF-RD coloring map, (b) phase distribution map, in which black lines represent the boundaries and green areas denote the γ precipitates, (c) TEM analysis of recrystallizing microstructure, (d) magnified view of area A in c, (e) elemental analysis along the line shown in d, (f) magnified view of area B in c, (g) grain boundary precipitation and element distribution maps, (h) HRTEM of precipitates, (i) IFFT image of the phase boundary marked by the red square in h.

Strength and ductility are inherently conflicting properties, where enhancing one typically reduces the other, as evident in the strength-elongation plot (Fig. S2). A similar trade-off exists between strength and electrical conductivity in the Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy. The electrical resistance ρ_i is mainly determined by the following factors [43]:

$$\rho_i = \rho_0 + \rho_{dis} + \rho_{gb} + \rho_{ss} + \rho_{ps} \quad (2)$$

where $\rho_0 = 1.724 \times 10^{-8} \Omega \cdot m$ is taken as the intrinsic resistance of pure Cu, ρ_{dis} is dislocation scattering resistivity, ρ_{gb} is interface scattering resistivity, ρ_{ss} is solute scattering resistivity, and ρ_{ps} is precipitate strain field scattering resistivity. Factors that enhance strength, e.g., dislocations, grain boundaries, solutes, and precipitates, also increase electron scattering, thereby reducing electrical conductivity. Among these, dislocations and large precipitates contribute weak scattering, while grain boundaries and solute atoms dominate [44]. In the cold-rolled sample, a single-phase solid solution (Fig. 1e) with high solid solubility of Ni and Sn induces strong electron scattering. Additionally, the grain refinement and dislocation multiplication caused by cold working further decrease the electrical conductivity (6.6 % IACS). After 1 h aging, the microstructure consists of recovered regions, spinodal decomposition products, and recrystallized grains with γ precipitates (Fig. 3c). Although the small particles from spinodal decomposition and γ precipitates increase electron scattering, this effect is overshadowed by the substantial decrease in the solute concentration (and dislocation density) in the α matrix, leading to a significant increase in electrical conductivity (9.7 % IACS). By 4-hour aging, extensive dislocation recovery, recrystallization, and precipitation of Ni/Sn-rich γ phases further reduce electron scattering, resulting in a conductivity of 11.7 % IACS. Concurrently, the nanotwins formed during the precipitation process not only refine the grains, thereby strengthening the alloy, but also have a minimal impact on conductivity owing to their coherent interfaces with the matrix [39].

In summary, a Cu-15Ni-9Sn alloy with both high strength and high electrical conductivity was successfully fabricated through cold rolling followed by aging treatment. The alloy achieved an ultimate tensile strength of 1131 MPa after aging at 400 °C for 1 hour. Spinodal decomposition, grain refinement and precipitation were identified as key contributors to its excellent tensile strength. Additionally, due to the precipitation depleting solid solution atoms, the electrical conductivity of the alloy is significantly improved. Most notably, a layered structure composed of nanotwins, α matrix, and γ precipitates was formed during the aging process, which is considered the crucial factor enabling the simultaneous enhancement of mechanical and electrical properties of the present alloy. This work provides a new route for in-situ production of nano-twinned Cu-Ni-Sn alloy by deformation and aging.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fei Yang: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Canhui Wu:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ruifeng Li:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Yusong Xu:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lichu Zhou:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Feng Fang:** Writing – review & editing. **Liming Dong:** Writing – review & editing. **Hyoung Seop Kim:** Writing – review & editing. **Wenyi Huo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Tianbo Yu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declarations and competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.scriptamat.2025.116834.

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